

Effect of Cryogenic Treatment Soaking Period on Mechanical Properties of Commercial Hydrocarbons

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ABSTRACT

Cryogenic treatment has emerged as an effective post-processing technique for improving the performance of polymeric materials. However, the response of different polymers to identical cryogenic conditions remains insufficiently understood. In the present study, the influence of cryogenic soaking period on the mechanical properties of two commercially important hydrocarbon polymers, namely linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE) and polypropylene (PP), was investigated. The polymers were subjected to cryogenic treatment at -185°C for soaking periods of 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 h. Tensile strength and percentage elongation were evaluated to assess the effect of treatment duration. Both polymers exhibited an initial improvement in mechanical performance with increasing soaking period, followed by deterioration at prolonged exposure times. LLDPE showed a maximum tensile strength of 16.60 MPa and elongation of 641% after 12 h of treatment, whereas PP exhibited a maximum tensile strength of 32.96 MPa and elongation of 381.38% after 8 h. PP demonstrated significantly greater strength enhancement, while LLDPE retained superior ductility throughout the treatment range. The differing responses were attributed to variations in polymer chain architecture and molecular mobility. The study demonstrates that the optimum cryogenic soaking period is polymer specific and that mechanically distinct responses can occur even among chemically similar hydrocarbon polymers.

Keywords: Cryogenic treatment; Linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE); Polypropylene (PP); Tensile strength; Percentage elongation; Polymer chain architecture

1. Introduction

Polymeric materials are extensively used in engineering, automotive, packaging and consumer applications because of their low density, ease of processing and favorable mechanical properties

[1,2]. Among commercially available polymers, linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE) and polypropylene (PP) are two of the most widely utilized hydrocarbon-based thermoplastics. Both materials consist primarily of carbon and hydrogen atoms and exhibit excellent chemical resistance, low cost and ease of manufacturing [1,3]. Despite their similar chemical composition, differences in molecular architecture, chain mobility and packing behavior result in significant variations in their mechanical performance and service characteristics [1,3].

In recent years, cryogenic treatment (CT) has emerged as a promising post-processing technique for improving the performance of engineering materials [4,5]. The process involves exposing materials to extremely low temperatures for a specified soaking period followed by controlled warming to room temperature. While cryogenic treatment has been extensively studied in metallic materials for enhancing hardness, wear resistance and dimensional stability, its application to polymers remains relatively limited [4-6]. Existing studies have shown that cryogenic exposure can alter polymer chain arrangement, crystallinity, molecular packing and residual stress state, thereby influencing mechanical and tribological behavior [6-9].

The effectiveness of cryogenic treatment in polymers is strongly dependent on treatment parameters, particularly the soaking period [7-10]. Insufficient soaking time may not allow adequate molecular rearrangement, whereas excessive exposure may reduce or even reverse the beneficial effects achieved during the initial stages of treatment. Therefore, determination of an optimum soaking period is important for maximizing property enhancement. Previous investigations on polyethylene, polypropylene, polyamide, PTFE and other engineering polymers have demonstrated that the response to cryogenic treatment varies significantly depending on polymer structure, chain mobility and degree of crystallinity [6-10].

LLDPE and PP provide an interesting platform for studying this behavior. Both polymers belong to the hydrocarbon family and are generally classified as non-polar thermoplastics. However, LLDPE possesses a relatively flexible polyethylene backbone containing short-chain branches, whereas PP contains pendant methyl groups attached to the polymer backbone [1,3]. The presence of these side groups influences chain mobility, packing efficiency and stiffness, which in turn affects mechanical performance. Consequently, the two polymers are expected to exhibit different responses when subjected to identical cryogenic treatment conditions.

Although several studies have investigated cryogenic treatment of individual polymers, direct comparisons between commercial hydrocarbon polymers exposed to identical cryogenic

conditions remain scarce in the literature [6-10]. Such comparative investigations are important for understanding the role of molecular architecture in governing cryogenic treatment effectiveness and for selecting suitable materials for applications requiring enhanced mechanical performance. In view of this, the present work investigates the effect of cryogenic treatment soaking period on the mechanical properties of two commercially important hydrocarbon polymers, namely LLDPE and polypropylene. Both materials were subjected to cryogenic treatment at -185°C for soaking periods ranging from 4 to 24 h. The influence of soaking period on tensile strength and percentage elongation was evaluated and compared. The observed property variations are discussed in relation to differences in molecular structure, chain mobility and packing behavior of the two polymers.

2. Experimental Details

2.1 Materials and Sample Preparation

Commercial grades of LLDPE (O35042) and PP (SRM100NC) were procured from Reliance Polymers in pellet form. Before processing, the pellets were dried at 100°C for 2 h to remove absorbed moisture. Test specimens were fabricated using an injection molding machine (Electronica Optima 75–128). For LLDPE, the barrel temperature was maintained between 110 and 140°C . For PP, the barrel temperature range was 145 - 175°C . The mold temperature was maintained at 70°C and the injection pressure was fixed at 80 MPa. A holding pressure of 35 MPa and a cooling time of 8 s were used for both materials to obtain defect-free molded specimens.

2.2 Cryogenic Treatment Procedure

Cryogenic treatment was carried out in an in-house developed cryogenic chamber using liquid nitrogen as the cooling medium. All specimens were treated at a constant temperature of -185°C . The soaking periods investigated were 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 h. To avoid thermal shock, the specimens were cooled gradually from room temperature (25°C) to the treatment temperature at a controlled cooling rate of $1^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. After completion of the designated soaking period, the specimens were returned to room temperature under controlled warming conditions at a heating rate of $1^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The same cryogenic treatment cycle was applied to both LLDPE and PP specimens.

2.3 Tensile Testing

Tensile properties were evaluated using Type-I dumbbell specimens in accordance with ASTM D638. The specimens had a gauge length of 65 mm and a cross-sectional dimension of $12\text{ mm} \times$

4 mm. Testing was performed using a Universal Testing Machine (International Equipments). A crosshead speed of 50 mm/min was employed for all tests. For each condition, three specimens were tested and the average value was reported.

3. Results and Discussion

The mechanical response of LLDPE and PP subjected to cryogenic treatment at -185°C was evaluated through tensile strength and percentage elongation measurements. To better understand the influence of cryogenic exposure, the effects of soaking period on tensile strength and elongation are discussed individually, followed by a comparative analysis of the role of polymer chain architecture in governing the observed behavior.

3.1 Effect of Cryogenic Soaking Period on Tensile Strength

The variation in tensile strength of LLDPE and PP as a function of cryogenic soaking period is shown in **Figure 1**. Both polymers exhibited a measurable response to cryogenic treatment; however, the extent of improvement and the optimum soaking period differed considerably.

Figure 1 Tensile strength of cryo-treated LLDPE and PP under study

For LLDPE, the tensile strength increased gradually from 15.79 MPa in the untreated condition to 16.60 MPa after 12 h of cryogenic treatment. This corresponds to an improvement of approx. 5%. The increase was progressive from 4 h to 12 h, indicating that the beneficial effects of cryogenic

exposure accumulated with increasing soaking duration. Beyond 12 h, the tensile strength decreased to 16.12 MPa at 16 h and then dropped sharply to 10.50 MPa and 9.53 MPa at 20 h and 24 h, respectively. These results indicate that 12 h represents the optimum soaking period for maximizing the tensile strength of LLDPE under the present treatment conditions.

The tensile strength response of PP was significantly different. The untreated PP specimen exhibited a tensile strength of 22.44 MPa. Following cryogenic treatment, the tensile strength increased rapidly and reached a maximum value of 32.96 MPa after 8 h of soaking. This corresponds to an improvement of approx. 46%, which is substantially higher than that observed for LLDPE. Further increases in soaking period resulted in a gradual reduction in tensile strength. Nevertheless, the values remained above the untreated condition up to 20 h of treatment. At 24 h, the tensile strength decreased to 20.27 MPa, which was slightly lower than the untreated value.

A comparison of the two polymers shows that PP exhibited a much stronger tensile-strength response to cryogenic treatment than LLDPE. While LLDPE achieved only a modest increase in strength, PP displayed a pronounced improvement during the initial stages of treatment. Furthermore, the optimum soaking period for PP was observed at 8 h, whereas LLDPE required 12 h to reach its maximum tensile strength. These observations indicate that the response of hydrocarbon polymers to cryogenic treatment is strongly material dependent and that identical processing conditions do not necessarily produce similar property enhancements [7-10].

3.2 Effect of Cryogenic Soaking Period on Percentage Elongation

Figure 2 shows the influence of cryogenic soaking period on the percentage elongation of LLDPE and PP. Unlike tensile strength, the elongation results reveal substantial differences in the ability of the two polymers to retain ductility during prolonged cryogenic exposure.

The untreated LLDPE specimen exhibited an elongation of 469%. With increasing soaking period, the elongation increased continuously and reached a maximum value of 641% after 12 h of treatment. This represents an improvement of approx. 36% over the untreated condition. Although a slight reduction was observed at longer soaking periods, the elongation remained above 600% throughout the range of 16-24 h. The results suggest that cryogenic treatment not only enhanced the tensile strength of LLDPE but also improved its ductility up to the optimum soaking period.

Figure 2 ELongation of cryo-treated LLDPE and PP under study

In the case of PP, the elongation increased from 263.87% in the untreated condition to 381.38% after 8 h of treatment, corresponding to an improvement of approx. 44%. However, unlike LLDPE, the elongation decreased rapidly beyond the optimum soaking period. The elongation dropped to 208.44% after 12 h and continued to decline with further treatment, reaching only 73.57% after 24 h. The decrease observed beyond 8 h was considerably more severe than that recorded for LLDPE. The elongation results clearly demonstrate the contrasting behavior of the two polymers under identical cryogenic conditions. LLDPE retained a high level of ductility even after prolonged soaking periods, whereas PP experienced a substantial loss in elongation once the optimum treatment duration was exceeded. The results indicate that although both polymers benefit from cryogenic treatment during the initial stages, their long-term response to extended soaking periods differs significantly [7-10].

3.3 Comparative Analysis of Cryogenic Response in LLDPE and PP

The tensile properties results presented above demonstrate that the two hydrocarbon polymers respond differently to identical cryogenic treatment conditions. While both materials exhibited an initial improvement in tensile strength and elongation, the magnitude of improvement and the optimum soaking period varied considerably. The most notable difference was observed in tensile strength. PP exhibited a maximum improvement of approximately 46.9%, whereas LLDPE

showed an increase of only 5%. Conversely, LLDPE maintained exceptionally high elongation values throughout the entire soaking period range, while PP experienced a rapid reduction in ductility beyond its optimum treatment duration. These observations indicate that the cryogenic response of a polymer is not governed solely by its chemical composition but also by its molecular architecture and deformation characteristics [2,3,11-13].

The proposed mechanism responsible for the different cryogenic responses of LLDPE and PP is illustrated schematically in **Figure 3**. Although both polymers belong to the hydrocarbon family and are composed primarily of carbon and hydrogen atoms, their molecular architectures differ considerably. These structural differences influence chain mobility, molecular packing behavior and deformation characteristics, ultimately governing the effectiveness of cryogenic treatment. The schematic highlights the role of chain flexibility, side-group effects and packing efficiency in determining the evolution of tensile strength and elongation with increasing soaking period.

Figure 3 Schematic illustration of the proposed mechanism responsible for the different cryogenic responses of LLDPE and PP

In the case of LLDPE, the polymer chains consist mainly of a flexible polyethylene backbone containing short-chain branches. The absence of bulky side groups allows greater molecular mobility and facilitates chain rearrangement during cryogenic exposure. As the soaking period increases, the chains can gradually attain a more favorable packing arrangement without severely restricting their ability to undergo deformation [3,11]. Consequently, LLDPE is known to exhibit high ductility and large elongation at break compared with many commodity thermoplastics [11,12]. LLDPE exhibits simultaneous improvements in both tensile strength and elongation up to the optimum soaking period of 12 h. Even beyond the optimum condition, the material retains a high degree of ductility, indicating that the flexible chain structure can accommodate cryogenically induced changes without significant embrittlement.

PP exhibits a markedly different response because of the presence of pendant methyl groups attached to the polymer backbone. These side groups introduce steric restrictions that limit chain mobility and reduce the freedom of molecular movement compared with LLDPE [3,12,13]. As a result, PP generally exhibits higher stiffness and strength but lower resistance to large plastic deformation [11-13]. During the initial stages of cryogenic treatment, the restricted chain structure appears to promote a more efficient load-bearing arrangement, resulting in a substantial increase in tensile strength. This explains the significant strength enhancement observed in PP after 8 h of treatment. However, as the soaking period increases beyond the optimum condition, the reduced molecular mobility limits the ability of the chains to undergo plastic deformation. As a result, the material experiences a rapid decline in elongation, indicating a progressively more brittle mechanical response.

A comparison of the two polymers therefore suggests that cryogenic treatment influences not only the magnitude of property improvement but also the balance between strength and ductility. LLDPE exhibits a ductility-dominated response characterized by moderate strengthening and excellent retention of elongation, whereas PP exhibits a strength-dominated response in which large gains in tensile strength are accompanied by a substantial loss of ductility at extended soaking periods. The results demonstrate that even among chemically similar hydrocarbon polymers, differences in chain architecture can significantly alter the manner in which cryogenic treatment affects mechanical performance. Consequently, the optimum soaking period is polymer specific and depends strongly on the interplay between chain flexibility, molecular packing characteristics and resistance to deformation [2,3,7-13].

4. Conclusions

The following conclusions can be made from the present study comparing the effect of cryogenic treatment on different commercial hydrocarbons:

- Cryogenic treatment improved the mechanical properties of both LLDPE and PP, however, the extent of improvement depended strongly on the soaking period.
- LLDPE exhibited optimum performance after 12 h of treatment, with simultaneous improvements in tensile strength and elongation, while retaining high ductility.
- PP showed a significantly higher tensile strength enhancement, achieving its optimum response after 8 h of treatment, but experienced a substantial reduction in elongation at longer soaking periods.
- The optimum soaking period was found to be polymer specific, indicating that identical cryogenic conditions do not produce similar responses in different hydrocarbon polymers.
- The contrasting behavior of LLDPE and PP demonstrates the important role of polymer chain architecture and molecular mobility in determining cryogenic treatment effectiveness.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement:

1. Abdurahman S. Bin Mazi: formal analysis; investigation; visualization; writing – original draft.

2. Prashant S. Kulkarni: validation; supervision.
3. Kavita Pande: conceptualization; methodology; resources.
4. Swamini Chopra: conceptualization; validation; writing – review & editing; supervision.

References

- [1] Callister WD, Rethwisch DG. *Materials Science and Engineering: An Introduction*. 10th ed. Hoboken (NJ): John Wiley & Sons; 2018.
- [2] Osswald TA, Menges G. *Materials Science of Polymers for Engineers*. 4th ed. Munich: Hanser Publishers; 2021.
- [3] Brydson JA. *Plastics Materials*. 8th ed. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann; 2017.
- [4] Barron RF. Cryogenic Treatment of Metals to Improve Wear Resistance. *Cryogenics*. 1982;22(8):409–413.
- [5] Das D, Dutta AK, Ray KK. Optimization of the duration of cryogenic processing to maximize wear resistance of AISI D2 steel. *Cryogenics*. 2009;49(3-4):176–184.
- [6] Baldissera P, Delprete C. Deep cryogenic treatment: A bibliographic review. *Open Mechanical Engineering Journal*. 2008;2:1–11.
- [7] Azhagaiah M, Gnanavelbabu A. Effect of cryogenic treatment on polymeric materials: A review. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 2020;27:2423–2428.
- [8] Kumar S, Singh R, Ahuja IPS. Investigations on mechanical behavior of cryogenically treated polymer materials: A review. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*. 2018;31(8):1031–1052.
- [9] Akhbarizadeh A, Javadpour S, Arefkhani M. Influence of cryogenic treatment on the tribological and mechanical properties of polymeric materials: A review. *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*. 2019;37:508–520.
- [10] Baldissera P, Delprete C. Effects of deep cryogenic treatment on static mechanical properties of polymeric materials. *Materials and Design*. 2010;31(10):4728–4734.
- [11] Peacock AJ. *Handbook of Polyethylene: Structures, Properties, and Applications*. New York: Marcel Dekker; 2000.
- [12] Karger-Kocsis J. *Polypropylene: Structure, Blends and Composites*. Volume 1. London: Chapman & Hall; 1995.

- [13] Ehrenstein GW. *Polymeric Materials: Structure, Properties, Applications*. Munich: Hanser Publishers; 2001.